

Evaluating Diversity of Staying People by Using High-resolution Gridded Population

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Keywords: differential entropy, population diversity, characteristics of residence

Abstract

Many urban planning master plans by local governments in Japan consider “interactions among diverse individuals” as a key factor in promoting urban vibrancy. Such interactions are more likely to occur when people from diverse backgrounds stay within the same urban spaces. However, while much research had addressed these interactions themselves, the quantitative evaluation of the diversity of the staying population in urban spaces has received limited attention. To support effective urban measures such as organizing events in open spaces, the diversity evaluation therein in advance is important.

This study proposes a method for such diversity evaluation at high spatial resolution. Although the diversity in individual's values and knowledge is difficult to observe directly, this study assumes that such diversity can be inferred from characteristics of their residential areas, for which data is often available. Specifically, we prepare 18 variables for each 1-kilometer grid such as age composition, family composition, employment status, and education level from national census data. These are aggregated into one-dimensional values via principal component analysis. We also utilize 500-meter grid-based population data derived from mobile phone location records, which are linked to users' places of residence in 1-kilometer grid. Consequently, for each 500-meter grid, we can determine the composition of the staying population based on residential characteristics. The diversity of the staying population is then calculated using differential entropy, a metric from information theory.

The results for two prefectures in Japan showed that high levels of diversity were found not only in central urban areas, large hospitals, and suburban shopping malls, but also in certain grids without any notable facilities. In these cases, the areas attracted people from residential areas with diverse characteristics. Furthermore, we identified several interesting cases where the level of diversity differed significantly among grids with similar facilities.